

ORTHOPEDIC TREATMENT OF PATIENTS WITH MALOCCLUSIONS OF THE FIRST AND SECOND CLASS ACCORDING TO ENGLE

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ABSTRACT

Diagnosis of anomalies of the dentofacial system is the most important task in the practice of an orthodontist, as it allows one to determine a treatment plan for the patient.

It is relevant to discuss the issue of indications for orthodontic treatment with the removal or preservation of individual teeth.

Purpose: To develop a method for planning orthodontic treatment, taking into account the possibility of preserving or removing individual teeth in order to increase the effectiveness of orthodontic treatment.

Tasks:

1. To study the anthropometric features of the structure of the dentition in patients with malocclusions who require tooth extraction before orthodontic treatment;
2. To study the X-ray cephalometric features of the structure of the facial skeleton of patients with malocclusions who require tooth extraction before orthodontic treatment;
3. Conduct a comparative analysis of biometric and x-ray cephalometric indicators for malocclusions requiring tooth extraction before orthodontic treatment;
4. Assess the immediate results of orthodontic treatment using a system for determining indications for preservation or removal of teeth.

Material and methods : To achieve the set objectives, we examined and treated patients with anomalies of the dentoalveolar system of the first and second classes according to Engle . The number of which was 100 people who were indicated for tooth extraction before orthodontic treatment. Their age ranged from 17 to 35 years: 56 of them were female, and 44 were male. To draw up a treatment plan for all patients, we carried out the following diagnostic measures: clinical examination, study of diagnostic models of the jaws and radiocephalometric analysis of teleroentgenograms of the head in a lateral projection before orthodontic treatment.

Distribution of patients admitted for treatment

Nosological form					
Angle Class I malocclusions		Engle class II malocclusions			
		I subclass		II subclass	
22		44		34	
Women	men	women	men	women	men
12	10	24	20	18	16

Angle class one malocclusions, all first premolars were extracted .

In the second group with malocclusions of the second class of the first subclass of Angle , the first upper premolars were removed .

Angle's class two malocclusions, the first upper premolars were also removed .

Angle class I and II malocclusions, we used the hardware method using non-removable orthodontic appliances (bracket system, straight - wire technique). Bracket systems with the Roth prescription were used in 81 cases, with the Damon prescription in 19 cases.

Results: The biometric features of the structure of the dentition were studied in case of malocclusions of the first and second class according to Engle in patients requiring tooth extraction before orthodontic treatment;

A comparative analysis of biometric and x-ray cephalometric indicators of patients with malocclusions of the first and second classes according to Engle , requiring tooth extraction before orthodontic treatment, and the norm was carried out using statistical research methods.

An expert system has been developed for determining indications for preserving or removing teeth when planning orthodontic treatment of malocclusions of the first and second class according to Engle .

CONCLUSIONS:

1. Anomalies of the dentofacial system of class I and II according to Engle are characterized by changes in many structures of the facial skeleton, including dentoalveolar and gnathic , the severity of which varies in individual nosological forms. If, in case of anomalies in the position of individual teeth, disturbances to a greater extent affect the dentoalveolar structures, then in the case of distal occlusion, both gnathic and skeletal structures are involved in the pathological process.

2. After treatment of Angle class I and II anomalies , the maximum expansion of the dentition in the area of the first premolars and first molars is achieved using the Damon technique , and the minimum - when treating with the removal of individual teeth and using the Roth technique .

3. For anomalies of the dentofacial system of class I according to Engle with a significant lack of space, a pronounced narrowing of the dentition in combination with a straight or convex facial profile, orthodontic treatment is most effective using the Damon technique .

4. When using self-ligating Passive type braces provide maximum expansion of the dentition, which allows for orthodontic treatment of anomalies of the dentofacial system without prior tooth extraction.

5. The greatest effectiveness of treatment of distal occlusion against the background of mandibular micro- and retrognathia is achieved using the Damon technique .

The indications for choosing the Roth and Damon fixed appliance technique developed during the study contribute to optimal planning and achievement of high results of orthodontic treatment.

References:

1. Akhmadov I. N. CLINICAL FEATURES AND PRINCIPLES OF TREATMENT OF ALLERGIC STOMATITIS WHEN USING PARTIAL AND COMPLETE REMOVABLE PLATE DENTURES //BBK 72 I66. – 2021. – P. 262.
2. Shavkatovich OR, Nizomitdin AI EFFECTIVENESS OF THE USE OF OSTEOPLASTIC MATERIAL" STIMUL-OSS" IN SAMARKAND //Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal. – 2022. – T. 3. – No. 11. – pp. 612-617.
3. Nizomitdin AI THERAPEUTIC EFFECT OF IMPROVED ENAMEL SURFACE PREPARATION TECHNIQUE IN THE TREATMENT OF ACUTE INITIAL CARIES OF TEMPORARY TEETH IN CHILDREN //Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal. – 2022. – T. 3. – No. 11. – pp. 440-445.
4. Akhmadov I. REVIEW OF MEANS FOR FIXATION OF DENTAL PROSTHESES // Collected Book of Scientific Practices SCIENTIFIC AND PRACTICAL CONFERENCE WITH INTERNATIONAL PARTICIPATION AND INITIAL TRAINING WITH INCIDENTAL PRACTICAL TECHNIQUES "CONVENTIONAL METHODS" DIAGNOSTICS, PREVENTION AND CARE OF MAIN DENTAL ILLNESSES." – 2021. – P. 43.
5. Nizomitdin AI Modern Methods of Odontopreparation for MetalCeramic for Beginner Prosthodontists //Eurasian Medical Research Periodical. – 2023. – T. 18. – S. 98-102.
6. Akhmadov I.N. Disturbances in the lipid peroxidation system in paradontosis //IQRO. – 2023. – T. 3. – No. 2. – pp. 124-127.
7. Sanaqulov J., Sadriyev N., Axmadov I. KERAMIK KIRITMANING BOSHQA RESTAVRATSIYA VOSITALARI BILAN SOLISHTIRISH // Central Asian magazine education And innovation _ – 2023. – T. 2. – No. 9 Part 2. – pp. 22-26.
8. Sadriyev N., Sanakulov J., Akhmedov I. ANALYSIS OF PROFILE TELERENTGOGRAM AND PLANNING ORTHODONTIC TREATMENT OF DENTAL ANOMALIES AND DEFORMATIONS IN CHILDREN AND ADOLESCENTS USING AUTOMATED EQUIPMENT WITH ELEMENTS ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE "ALLEGRO" // Eurasian magazine technologies And innovation _ – 2023. – T. 1. – No. 9. – pp. 69-71.
9. Akhmadov I. CERAMIC INLAY COMPARED WITH OTHER RESTORATIVE PROCEDURES //Eurasian Journal of Medical and Natural Sciences. – 2023. – T. 3. – No. 9. – pp. 126-131.

10. Akhmadov I. VARK DEPARTMENT OF ORTHOPEDIC DENTISTRY //Eurasian Journal of Medical and Natural Sciences. – 2023. – T. 3. – No. 9. – pp. 132-136.
 11. Akhmadov I. et al. VARK DEPARTMENT OF ORTHOPEDIC DENTISTRY // Central Asian magazine education And innovation _ – 2023. – T. 2. – No. 10 Part 3. – pp. 57-61.
 12. Akhmadov I. et al. CERAMIC INLAYS COMPARED TO OTHER RESTORATION PROCEDURES // Eurasian magazine technologies And innovation _ – 2023. – T. 1. – No. 10. – pp. 186-191.
 13. Sadriev N. et al. DENTAL IMPLANTOLOGY IN THE DIABETIC PATIENTS // Bulletin students new Uzbekistan . – 2023. – T. 1. – No. 10. – pp. 44-48.
 14. Sadriev N. et al. DENTAL IN CHILDREN WITH TRAUMATIC STOMATITIS COMPLEX DENTAL TREATMENT OF DISEASES AND THEIR EVALUATION OF PREVENTION // Central Asian magazine education And innovation _ – 2023. – T. 2. – No. 10 Part 3. – pp. 62-65.
 15. Sadriev N. et al. PREVENTION OF PROSTHETIC DENTISTRY // Bulletin teachers new Uzbekistan . – 2023. – T. 1. – No. 10. – pp. 54-57.
 16. Sanakulov Zh., Sadriev N., Akhmadov I. COMPLEX ORTHOPEDIC-SURGICAL TREATMENT OF ANOMALIES AND DEFORMATIONS OF THE DENTAL SYSTEM IN A FORMED BITE USING LASER TECHNOLOGIES ABSTRACT // Central Asian Journal of Education and Innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – No. 9 Part 2. – pp. 27-31.
 17. Jamshed S. PREVALENCE OF PHYSIOLOGICAL BITE FORMS IN PEOPLE WITH DIFFERENT FACE TYPES //Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal. – 2022. – T. 3. – No. 11. – S. 451-454.
 18. Nazhmiddinovich SN, Obloberdievich SJ Optimization of Orthopedic Treatment of Dentition Defects in Patients with Chronic Diseases of the Gastrointestinal Tract //Eurasian Research Bulletin. – 2023. – T. 17. – S. 157-159.
 19. Obloberdievich SJ Grade States Fabrics Periodontal by Clinical Indexes //Scholastic: Journal of Natural and Medical Education. – 2023. – T. 2. – No. 5. – pp. 175-180.
 20. Sanakulov Zhamshed Obloberdi ugli , Zubaydullaeva Maftuna Alisher kizi , & Norbutaev Alisher Berdikulovich . (2022). CLINICAL AND EPIDEMIOLOGICAL RESULTS OF ORTHOPEDIC TREATMENT OF PATIENTS WITH PARTIAL ABSENCE OF TOOTH. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal* , 10 (1), 958-960. Retrieved from <https://www.giirj.com/index.php/giirj/article/view/1171>
 21. Nazhmiddinovich SN OPTIMIZATION OF ORTHOPEDIC TREATMENT OF DENTAL DEFECTS IN PATIENTS WITH CHRONIC GASTROINTESTINAL DISEASES //Spectrum Journal of Innovation, Reforms and Development. – 2022. – T. 10. – S. 53-58.
- Najmiddinovich SN et al. CARIES IN SCHOOL CHILDREN AND TREATMENT PREVENTIVE MEASURES //American Journal of Pedagogical and Educational Research.